

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF THE PEOPLE OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14044665>

INTRODUCTION. People of pedagogy — this is our people 's historical experiences, traditions , and values on the basis formed education system. Higher education institutions in the people's pedagogy of teaching, not only the students theoretical knowledge to increase, but also them in practice apply to get abilities development also service makes.

People of pedagogy — this nation's historical experience, traditions and values on the basis formed education system. This system not only to students theoretical knowledge to give, but also them practical in your life to apply this teaching also important is professional is.

MAIN PART. People pedagogical, first of all, national identitetni storage and consolidation , an important role plays. It is the students their people, history, culture and values about deep knowledge gives. Also, people pedagogy of the basic principles, for example, ethical discipline, diligence, mutual respect , such as the concepts of the young generation of individuals as in the growth of the great importance it has. People of pedagogy — this nation's historical experience, traditions and values on the basis formed education system. This system not only to students theoretical knowledge to give, but also them practical in life to apply in teaching is also an important role to have. Folk pedagogy the importance of the following aspects seen can be:

1. ***National identitetni save.*** People of pedagogy national identitetni in maintaining an important role plays. Pupils their own people, the history, the culture, the traditions of study through self means. This process, in its turn, the young generation of his people to the love and respect increases.

2. ***Historical tajribaning needs to learn.*** People pedagogy in their people 's historical experience on the basis of learning and education to give an important role has. Pupils from the people of heroism, of ulug'lar life and activities about to learn, their historical root of the mean. This while them their future responsibility with the approach to motivate.

3. ***Values and moral education.*** Values learned on the basis of folk pedagogy - moral education, hard work, mutual respect - are important for the growth of the young generation as individuals. These values educational on

ethical decisions, take to, others with relationships establish , and the community in an active and take part to the abilities you will develop.

4. **Cultural heritage support.** People of pedagogy the cultural heritage conservation and development have also an important role plays. Students, people art, traditions and customs of the study through the culture of the duration will provide. This, in its turn, its people, culture and the art of raising serve will.

5. **Social integration.** People pedagogical with the help of students of social integration in the process involved are. They have mutual mutual respect, harmony and cooperation, the principles of study through society in an active and responsible citizens to be reaching brings.

Higher education institutions in the people's pedagogy teaching for qualified teachers need. Teachers people of pedagogy on their knowledge updated they go, modern pedagogical methods, mastering and educational process in innovative technologies to apply they should. Higher education institutions in the people's pedagogy teaching for qualified teachers in the preparation of an important role has. Teachers professional preparation not only educational process efficiency increases, but also the students for twofat educational environment creates.

CONCLUSION. People of pedagogy higher education institutions in teaching, future generation of national values with to become familiar, to them , educate and person as in the formation has an important role to have. This while its in turn, society, cultural and spiritual development service will. In this regard, the people's pedagogy of the teaching process and attention to focus and it effectively organize to need increasingly growing has been.

People pedagogical significance, first of all, his education in the process of the role and learners' personal development in the effects of it show up will. National identitetni storage, ethical values development and cultural heritage support through people's pedagogy of the young generation the right way to choose and future active citizens be reached help will. This process, in its turn, society, cultural and spiritual development service will.

Folk pedagogy for teaching interactive lessons, practical sessions and independent studies , such as methods of the application, students for effective learning environment creates. These methods not only theoretical knowledge to increase, but also the students practical skills development also service makes. As a result, pupils have a people's pedagogy of the basic principles of the depth mean, them life used to get a chance to have a will.

Higher education institutions in the people's pedagogy teaching for qualified teachers preparation process, their knowledge update, modern pedagogical methods, mastering and innovative technologies for use through out carried. This process not only teachers, but also students for also useful be, the educational process, the efficiency increases and the people of pedagogical development service will. Teachers personal and professional development, as well as, education quality in increasing an important factor is.

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